

**SOLVING PROBLEMS RELATED TO CALCULATION AND
VERIFICATION IN ELEMENTARY CLASSES****Aydarbekova Gulzar¹**¹Nukus district, school number 4 elementary school teacher**Kaniyazova Rano²**²Nukus city, school number 17 elementary school teacher<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7524714>

Annotation: This article is about calculus problems in elementary grades, solving calculus problems, and calculus problems in the field of formulas.

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Depending on the way the condition of the problem is not changed, geometrical problems can be divided into calculable geometrical problems, and geometrical problems related to verification. Let's focus separately on the geometrical problems related to the flow:

The theoretical knowledge acquired in geometrical problems, like any other problem, was improved, the results could be put into practice, and the properties and properties of geometrical figures were used in a scientific experiment. All scientific experiments are formed in the process of implementation of practical exercises.

The relevant problems are the theoretical knowledge acquired from the students in practice in each branch of geometry, the equations generated in the learning process, the relationships between the elements of geometrical figures, while the properties of the elements are used, such as length, length, area, volume, etc. For example, it is possible to enter into the composition of the problems related to the calculation of problems related to the calculation of the length of the part, the length of the part, the balance of the rod, and the balance of the surface of the rod. It is possible to include in the set of geometrical problems to be verified the properties of geometrical figures and the relations between the elements of geometrical figures from a theoretical point of view.

When solving geometrical problems related to verification, it is necessary to be able to clearly distinguish the problems given in the problem, the conditions of the problem, and the problem, to have some theoretical knowledge, to be able to analyze and synthesize methods.

General mathematics can be divided into problems related to the verification of theorems, equality, and inequalities. It should be said that from high school mathematics, almost all theorems were confirmed.

In the high school geometry class, it was possible to include such problems:

Prove the theorem of sines:

Prove the theorem of cosines

A summary of the results of the formulas:

- Heron's formula (here p -semi-perimeter);

through medians;

- due to the height of the legs;

Calculate the median of participation and derive the formulas. Bringing out formulas for calculating the balance of cooperation. (1)

We will consider the issue in the relevant section. problem Confirm that the balance of participation can be explained by formulas (1) by means of its components.

Let's go. Let's assume that we are given a segment ABC , and the lengths of its sides are $AB=c$ $BC=a$ $AC=b$. Let there be a balance between us and us. If we set $AN=x$, then $NC=b-x$.

Fields are problems that need to be calculated using the formula.

1. Information about field.
2. Non-standard units.
3. Fields are problems to be calculated using the formula.

Area (in mathematics) is one of the quantities used to describe geometric figures on a plane or surface. In particular, the surface is calculated by the number of squares that fill a flat figure, and the number of squares whose adjacent side is equal to the unit of length.

Surface calculation is an old practical geom. One of the most important issues of foreign affairs has come and gone (for example, dividing the fields). Calculating the area of a polygon in a plane depends on the possibility of dividing any polygon into quadrilaterals. It's the same as the 4-year-old's love for the field.

He found it necessary to compare the cross-sections in the readings before molding the face of the form, and to clarify the "big", "small", and "equal" relationships. In this work, it is possible to create clear ideas about the comparison of the objects and their functions. It is necessary to perform the following steps: cut out all kinds of wrinkles on lined paper. Let's have a look at this back.

In Salistrıwlaw, the following rules were set: if the first form is too big, if the second one is too big, then the second one is too small.

But when comparing two uniforms, it is not always clear which of them is bigger (equal). For example,

There are many solutions when analyzing forms. We come to the opinion that it is necessary to solve the problems of the past. In this case, it is appropriate to use the analogy of measuring sections. For example, the length of the table could not be placed on top of the wardrobe. The numbers calculated separately from the lengths obtained are compared.

In the comparison, the following criteria were set:

if the first form is too big, the second one is too big.

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For the unbiased replacement of chickens, the following equipment is used: Chickens are kept in 3 cages with 8 chickens, and in 4 cages with 5 chickens. How many chickens are there?

Such problems can be solved $3 \times 8 - 4 \times 5 = 24 - 20 = 4$ times. He solved the educational problem graphically. Those who put the chicken in the strip of the leaky cage, marked the leak in the form of a trap:

The number of cells in each of the cells was determined, and in some cases, the number of cells was too large. After a few steps were taken, the flow began to gather: for comparison, every form should be divided into equal squares and counted, and if there are many squares in some, the number is slightly larger.

1. Upgrade. We have already known that all things are different. It shows how much space the form takes up. Juzbul became a member, and the reason is that it is possible to compare it.

2. The possibility of using even triangles in addition to equal squares is explained by examples when comparing faces to flows for the purpose of forming dreams about a unit square.

Which of the four animals in the picture has the biggest face? They came to the conclusion that it is impossible to compare them with the number of people who came to the question.

If it is a number, it is possible to find any number of different parts of the form, but you will stay here, therefore fully defined units are accepted. Cut out the sections with a straight line sewing machine with cm, dm, m measurements.

The surface is so square. cm, sq. dm, sq. Square olshevs with m width were used.

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The word "square centimeter" is analyzed and it appears that it is a square whose length is 1 cm. In order to distinguish a square unit from a linear unit, it is useful to replace such units: a square unit with a length of 1 cm, 3 cm and 3 square meters. filter cm. As a result of solving the problems, the number of squares into which the left shape can be divided is said to be the face of the form.

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